

PRODUCTION AND MARKETING CONSTRAINTS FACED BY HONEY BEEKEEPERS IN KOLHAPUR DISTRICT OF MAHARASHTRA: A GARRETT RANKING APPROACH

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Abstract

Beekeeping is emerging as a vital subsidiary enterprise for augmenting farmers' income and providing nutritional security. Despite its potential, honey producers face several challenges that limit productivity and marketing efficiency. The present study was conducted in Kolhapur district of Maharashtra with the objective of identifying and ranking the major constraints in honey production and marketing. Primary data were collected from beekeepers through a structured interview schedule, and the Henry Garrett Ranking technique was employed to analyze the relative importance of constraints. The findings revealed that Pest and Disease Infestation - It received a mean score of 69.85 for small-scale, 71.30 for medium-scale, and 67.35 for large-scale operations and was ranked I, I, and II accordingly. overall mean score for this problem was 69.50 which was ranked I. also unfavorable weather conditions, pesticide poisoning, and absconding of bees were major production constraint, while in marketing constraint price variation issues were noted as they were receiving lower prices due to inadequate direct market access and exploitation by middlemen. The mean scores obtained were 65 for small-scale, 54.65 for medium-scale, and 69.2 for large-scale producers, with ranks of II, III, and I respectively. overall mean score for this problem was 62.95 which was ranked I, inadequate market information, and insufficient storage facilities emerged as the foremost marketing problems. Based on the mean scores across all groups, pest and disease incidence, unfavorable weather conditions, and absconding of bees emerged as the top three production problems faced by beekeepers. The major marketing problems identified were price variation and inadequate market information, which ranked highest overall among beekeepers. The results highlight the need for policy interventions such as promotion of bee-friendly farming practices, provision of easy credit facilities, development of efficient market networks, and branding of honey to strengthen apiculture as a sustainable rural enterprise.

Keywords: Production, Marketing, Constraints, Honey, Garrett Ranking, Beekeeper, Apiculture, and Beekeeping

Introduction:

Apiculture has emerged as one of the most promising subsidiary enterprises in India, offering livelihood opportunities, pollination benefits, and a source of nutritious food. Honey and other hive products not only contribute to rural household income but also play an important role in agricultural sustainability. India is among the major honey producers in the world, with Maharashtra occupying a significant position due to its diverse Agro-climatic conditions and rich floral diversity. Within Maharashtra, Kolhapur district has gradually become a notable hub for beekeeping activities. Despite its potential, the growth of apiculture is hindered by several constraints faced by beekeepers. Production-related challenges such as pest and disease incidence, pesticide poisoning, absconding of bee colonies, scarcity of flowering resources, and adverse weather conditions often lead to fluctuations in honey yield. On the other hand, marketing constraints including lack of proper market information, weak linkages and networks, price instability, poor transportation and storage facilities, and absence of branding restrict beekeepers from realizing fair prices and expanding their market access. Understanding these problems is essential for designing effective policies and support systems to promote honey production as a sustainable enterprise. To address this, the present study aims to identify and rank the major production and marketing constraints faced by beekeepers in Kolhapur district. The Henry Garrett Ranking technique was employed to evaluate the relative importance of these constraints as perceived by respondents, thereby providing useful insights for policymakers, extension agencies, and farmer organizations.

Methodology

This study was carried out in Kolhapur district of Maharashtra, chosen for its favourable climate and growing interest in beekeeping as a supplementary livelihood. The district has a notable concentration of beekeepers and honey production, making it a suitable location for the research. A total of 60 beekeepers were selected from Bhudargad tehsil of Kolhapur district using stratified random sampling. To ensure

balanced representation, participants were grouped into small, medium, and large-scale beekeepers based on the number of bee colonies they maintained. Equal numbers were chosen from each category to capture differences in production and marketing challenges. Data were collected through a structured interview schedule tailored to the study. The questionnaire covered socio-economic details, production methods, and constraints faced in both honey production and marketing. Common production issues included pest and disease attacks, poor flowering, pesticide exposure, weather changes, bee absconding, financial limitations, and lack of access to technology. Marketing challenges involved limited market information, weak networks, price instability, unregulated markets, and inadequate transport, storage, and branding. To rank the severity of these problems, the Henry Garrett Ranking Technique was used. Beekeepers were asked to prioritize the listed constraints, helping to identify the most critical issues affecting their operations.

Data Analysis

To assess the severity and prioritization of the constraints, the Henry Garrett Ranking Technique was employed. Beekeepers were asked to rank the listed problems based on their perceived impact. The ranks were then converted into scores using Garrett's conversion table, and the mean scores were calculated to determine the most critical constraints affecting beekeeping operations. This technique used to evaluate the constraints faced by the respondents during production and marketing. The order of rank assigned by the respondents for all the factors was converted into scores using the given formula:

$$\text{Per cent position} = \frac{100 (R_{ij} - 0.50)}{N_j}$$

Where,

R_{ij} = rank given for i^{th} item by j^{th} individual,

N_j = number of items ranked by j^{th} individual

The estimated percentage position of each rank was converted into score with the help of Garrett's table. For each constraint, the scores of each respondent were added and the mean

score was calculated. The constraint with highest mean score was give 1st rank, considered most important constraint and others were ranked successively.

Result and Discussion

1. Identify the Problems faced in production and marketing of honey

The success of beekeeping business significantly depends on beekeepers' capacity to address various challenges encountered in production and marketing. Although apiculture has the potential to be profitable, many beekeepers face an obstacle that impede effective honey production and access to markets. These problems differ in nature, ranging to environmental and biological factors as well as institutional and infrastructural constraints. In order to analyze these challenges systematically, this study gathered data from a respondent's beekeepers about the main issues they experience in honey production and marketing. The problems that were identified were then classified, categorized, and ranked to identify their relative significance and effect on the beekeeping business.

1.1 Problems in production of honey

To identify the main challenges in honey production, beekeepers were surveyed to evaluate seven significant issues commonly faced throughout the production process. Table 1 and Fig 1 represent These issues were analyzed within small, medium, and large-scale categories, with the average score calculated for each problem. Ranks were then assigned based on these scores to highlight the most critical concerns for each group. Pest and Disease Infestation - It received a mean score of 69.85 for small-scale, 71.30 for medium-scale, and 67.35 for large-scale operations and was ranked I, I, and II accordingly. overall mean score for this problem was 69.50 which was ranked I. This is a first important and major problem faced by beekeepers which attacks from pests and diseases on bee colonies, including wax moths, mites, and foulbrood, were identified as a primary issue by beekeepers. The similar findings were observed in findings of Mmasa (2007) and

Gebrehiwot (2015), who identified pest infestation as the leading production challenge faced by beekeepers in Tanzania.

Then weather Condition It received a mean score of 60.25 for small-scale, 63.15 for medium-scale, and 71.05 for large-scale operations and was ranked II, II, and I accordingly. overall mean score for this problem was 64.82 which was ranked II. This is second important problem because of unpredictable rainfall patterns, elevated humidity levels, and extreme temperatures frequently disrupt colony strength and honey production Then Absconding of bees, it received a mean score of 57.80 for small-scale, 59.60 for medium-scale, and 63.4 for large-scale operations and was ranked III, III, and III accordingly. overall mean score for this problem was 60.27 which was ranked III. The third major problem was because of over crowing in colony population bees are abscond. Pesticide poisoning it received a mean score of 55.40 for small-scale, 53.75 for medium-scale, and 48.05 for large-scale operations and was ranked IV, IV, and IV accordingly. overall mean score for this problem was 52.40 which was ranked IV. The fourth least problem was because of farming spraying pesticide harmful to bees.

Lack of finance This issue received mean scores of 47.65, 43.85 and 28 across different group sizes and was ranked V, V, and V in small, medium, and large group accordingly. Overall, this problem was ranked V. Lack of technology It received a mean score of 38.45 for small-scale, 38.55 for medium-scale, and 30.85 for large-scale operations and was ranked VI, VI, and VI accordingly. overall mean score for this problem was 35.95 which was ranked VI and this problem was least, A lack of understanding regarding scientific beekeeping practices and insufficient extension services represented another significant challenge. And last. The similar findings were observed in findings of Kumar and Agarwal (2011), And last Lack of flowering it received a mean score of 22 for small-scale, 22 for medium-scale, and 44.4 for large-scale operations and was ranked VII, VII, and V accordingly. overall mean score for this problem was 29.47 which was ranked VII. A deficit in adequate nectar and pollen sources, particularly during off-seasons.

Table 1. Problems in production of honey

Sl. No	Production problems	Small (N=20)		Medium (N=20)		Large (N=20)		Overall (N=60)	
		Mean Score	Rank	Mean Score	Rank	Mean score	Rank	Mean Score	Rank
1	Pest and disease	69.85	I	71.30	I	67.35	II	69.5	I
2	lack of Flowering	22	VII	22	VII	44.4	v	29.47	VII
3	Pesticide Poisoning	55.4	IV	53.75	IV	48.05	IV	52.4	IV
4	Weather Condition	60.25	II	63.15	II	71.05	I	64.82	II
5	Absconding of Bees	57.8	III	59.6	III	63.4	III	60.27	III
6	Lack of Finance	47.65	V	43.85	V	28	VII	39.83	V
7	Lack of Technology	38.45	VI	38.55	VI	30.85	VI	35.95	VI

Based on the mean scores across all groups, pest and disease incidence, unfavorable weather conditions, and absconding of bees emerged as the top three production problems faced by beekeepers. Issues like lack of finance, pesticide poisoning, and lack of technology were also noted, while lack of flowering was the least concerning across all scales.

Fig. No 1 Problems in production of honey

1.2. Problems in marketing of honey

To evaluate the challenges faced in honey marketing, beekeepers were asked to prioritize seven significant issues. Table 2 and fig 2 represents the Mean scores were determined for small, medium, and large groups, and ranks were assigned based on these scores. The following issues were noted as Price Variation Beekeepers stated that they were receiving lower prices due to inadequate direct market access and exploitation by middlemen. The mean scores obtained were 65 for small-scale, 54.65 for medium-scale, and 69.2 for large-scale producers, with ranks of II, III, and I respectively. overall mean score for this problem was 62.95 which was ranked I. Inadequate market information it received a mean score of 69.05 for small-scale, 64.65 for medium-scale, and 46.5 for large-scale operations and was ranked I, I, and V accordingly. overall mean score for this problem was 60.07 which was ranked II. Farmers were not provided with timely information regarding market prices, demand, and potential buyers.

Insufficient Storage it received a mean score of 53.35 for small-scale, 50.75 for medium-scale, and 58.8 for large-scale operations and was ranked III, VI, and III accordingly. overall mean score for this problem was 54.30 which was ranked III. Inadequate storage for honey infrastructure and processing impacted its quality and shelf life. The similar findings were observed in findings of Kumar and Agarwal (2011), Unregulated market it received a mean score of 38.80 for small-scale, 60.90 for medium-scale, and 49.25 for large-scale operations and was ranked VI, II, and IV accordingly. overall mean score for this problem was 49.65 which was ranked IV. The lack of organized and regulated markets posed barriers to achieving fair price discovery. Absence of branding it received a mean score of 38.50 for small-scale, 40.10 for medium-scale, and 65.95 for large-scale operations and was ranked VII, VI, and II accordingly. overall mean score for this problem was 48.18 which was ranked V. Access to suitable packaging materials and branding resources was restricted, diminishing market appeal.

Table 2. Problems in marketing of honey

Sl. No	Marketing Problems	Small (N=20)		Medium (N=20)		Large (N=20)		Overall (N=60)	
		Mean Score	Rank	Mean Score	Rank	Mean score	Rank	Mean Score	Rank
1	Inadequate market information	69.05	I	64.65	I	46.5	V	60.07	II
2	weak market linkage and Networks	38.85	V	34.2	VII	26.7	VII	33.25	VII
3	Price Variation	65	II	54.65	III	69.2	I	62.95	I
4	Unregulated Market	38.8	VI	60.9	II	49.25	IV	49.65	IV
5	Inadequate Transportation facilities	49.85	IV	47.75	V	36.6	VI	44.73	VI
6	Insufficient Storage	53.35	III	50.75	VI	58.8	III	54.3	III
7	Absence of Branding	38.5	VII	40.1	VI	65.95	II	48.18	V

Fig. No.2 Problems of Marketing of honey

Inadequate transportation facilities it received a mean score of 49.85 for small-scale, 47.75 for medium-scale, and 36.6 for large-scale operations and was ranked IV, V, and VI accordingly. overall mean score for this problem was 44.73 which was ranked VI. Transporting honey from distant production locations to market centers increased the marketing burden. Weak market linkage and Networks it received a mean score of 38.85 for small-scale, 34.20 for medium-scale, and 26.7 for large-scale operations and was ranked V, VII, and VII

accordingly. overall mean score for this problem was 33.25 which was ranked VII.

The major marketing problems identified were price variation and inadequate market information, which ranked highest overall among beekeepers. Insufficient storage and unregulated markets also posed notable challenges, while weak market linkages and absence of branding were relatively less severe for small and medium farmers but significant for large-scale producers.

Suggestions to Overcome Constraints

Based on the findings of the study, the following measures are suggested to address the major production and marketing constraints faced by beekeepers in Kolhapur district:

1. **Promotion of bee-friendly practices** – Farmers should be encouraged to reduce pesticide use during flowering periods to minimize bee poisoning.
2. **Financial support and credit access** – Provision of low-interest institutional credit or subsidies for small beekeepers will ease financial constraints.
3. **Training and technology dissemination** – Regular training programs on colony management, disease control, and modern beekeeping technologies should be organized.
4. **Strengthening market linkages** – Establishing cooperative marketing systems and Farmer Producer Organizations (FPOs) can help in collective bargaining and assured market outlets.
5. **Price stabilization and branding** – Efforts should be made to regulate honey prices, promote branding, and develop quality certification to enhance consumer trust.
6. **Infrastructure development** – Improved transportation, storage, and processing facilities are essential to reduce marketing losses and enhance value addition.

Conclusion

The study clearly revealed that beekeeping in Kolhapur district, despite its potential as a profitable subsidiary enterprise, is constrained by several production and marketing challenges. Among production problems, Pest and adverse weather conditions, and absconding of bees were perceived as the most severe constraints, while in marketing, Price Variation, Inadequate market information, and Insufficient Storage were the foremost hurdles. The Garrett Ranking analysis helped to systematically identify and prioritize these issues from the perspective of beekeepers. The findings highlight the urgent need for policy and institutional interventions such as promotion of bee-friendly farming practices, provision of credit facilities, training in scientific management of colonies, development of efficient market networks, and branding of honey to improve market competitiveness. Strengthening cooperative efforts and farmer producer organizations (FPOs) can also enhance bargaining power and market access for beekeepers. Overall, addressing these production and marketing constraints will not only improve the profitability of honey production but also contribute to sustainable rural livelihoods, agricultural diversification, and ecological balance through enhanced pollination services.

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